

Notes

Polynuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Nickel(II)- and Cobalt(II)-salicylaldehyde

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USING Ni(SalH)₂ and Co(SalH)₂ as 'metal complex ligands'¹⁻³, in this paper, we describe a few oxygen bridged polynuclear⁴ complexes of alkali metal salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of Ni(SalH)₂ or Co(SalH)₂ and alkali metal salts in the ratio of 1 : 2 in absolute ethanol for 2-3 h. The whole thing went into solution and the adducts precipitated from hot solutions.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data suggest the general formula [M_a-(SalH)₂(M_bL)₂], where M_a = Ni or Co, and M_bL = Li, Na or K salts of deprotonated

8-hydroxyquinoline or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol. The colour of the adducts are different from those of the metal complex ligands. The higher decomposition temperatures of these adducts, compared to that of the metal complex ligands, indicated strong bonding between oxygen atom of metal complex ligands and the alkali metal ions. The adducts were stable under dry condition. The colour, decomposition temperatures and other properties of the adducts are given in Table 1.

The magnetic moment of octahedral trimer [Ni-(SalH)₂]₃ is 3.35 B.M., whereas the adducts have moments 3.5-3.8 B.M. These higher magnetic moments may be due to the change in geometry. Co(SalH)₂ is also an octahedral tetramer with magnetic moment 5.0 B.M. For the corresponding trinuclear alkali metal adducts, the magnetic moments have been observed in the range 4.5-4.75 B.M. The lower magnetic moment values suggest a change in geometry from octahedral to tetrahedral.

Infrared spectral measurements were made in nujol for the ligands and complexes between 4 000 and 600 cm⁻¹. Selected absorption bands are given in Table 1. In salicylaldehyde molecule, due to intra-hydrogen bonding, the C=O (aldehydic carbonyl) frequency show up at 1 665 cm⁻¹. The C—O (phenolic) stretch is observed in the free ligand at 1 282 cm⁻¹; on complexation with transition metals, this band shifts to higher energy by about 40-50 cm⁻¹, indicating phenolic oxygen coordination

TABLE 1

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Magnetic moment at 29°	Selected ir bands (cm ⁻¹)	
			N	Ni/Co	Na/K		C=O	C—O
Ni(SalH) ₂ ≡L	Green	270				3.35		
(LiIN2N) ₂ .L	Brown	280	3.85 (4.20)	8.4 (8.8)		3.50	1 640	1 345
(NaIN2N) ₂ .L	Brown	285	4.2 (4.0)	7.95 (8.40)	6.4 (6.6)	3.55	1 640	1 340
(KIN2N) ₂ .L	Dark brown	290	3.9 (3.8)	8.3 (8.0)	10.4 (10.8)	3.65	1 630	1 340
(Li8HQ) ₂ .L	Green	278	2.2 (2.3)	9.3 (9.6)		3.60	1 630	1 330
(Na8HQ) ₂ .L	Green	282-83	2.05 (2.20)	8.8 (9.1)	3.2 (3.6)	3.65	1 630	1 330
(K8HQ) ₂ .L	Dark green	285	1.89 (2.01)	8.4 (8.7)	5.4 (5.8)	3.80	1 635	1 330
Co(SalH) ₂ ≡L'	Yellow	275				5.00		
(LiIN2N) ₂ .L'	Red	300	4.0 (4.2)	8.45 (8.90)		4.50	1 645	1 340
(NaIN2N) ₂ .L'	Red	285	3.8 (4.0)	8.0 (8.4)	6.2 (6.6)	4.65	1 640	1 335
(KIN2N) ₂ .L'	Red	290	3.84 (3.80)	7.6 (8.0)	9.8 (10.8)	4.75	1 640	1 335
(Li8HQ) ₂ .L'	Dark brown	285	2.1 (2.8)	9.4 (9.7)		4.55		
(Na8HQ) ₂ .L'	Brown	280	2.35 (2.20)	9.4 (9.2)	3.2 (3.6)	4.70		1 330
(K8HQ) ₂ .L'	Dark brown	285	2.0 (2.1)	8.5 (8.8)	5.4 (5.8)	4.70	1 640	1 335

of the salicylaldehyde. This upward shift is due to the maintenance of a ring current arising out of electron delocalisation in the chelate ring.

In case of $\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2$, which is a trimer, the aldehydic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ and the phenolic $\text{C}-\text{O}$, both split into two; the aldehydic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ show up at 1 655 and 1 636 cm^{-1} , whereas phenolic $\text{C}-\text{O}$ can be spotted out at 1 355 and 1 322 cm^{-1} . Looking into the crystal structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$, it is found that half the oxygen atoms of aldehydic and phenolic ones, are bridged oxygens, *i.e.* one oxygen attached to two Ni^{2+} ions. The other half (6 oxygen atoms, comprising of 3 aldehydic and 3 phenolic oxygen atoms) oxygen atoms are terminal ones, *i.e.* they are attached to only one Ni^{2+} ion. The Co^{2+} -salicylaldehyde is also polynuclear, where two aldehydic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ at 1 655 and 1 627 cm^{-1} and two phenolic $\text{C}-\text{O}$ at 1 354 and 1 321 cm^{-1} have been reported. It can be generalised that in metal salicylaldehydes, when they are monomers, the aldehydic $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and phenolic $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ show only one normal peak at 1 650 cm^{-1} and 1 320 cm^{-1} , respectively; whereas when it is a polymer with oxygen bridges, both the aldehydic and phenolic frequencies split into two, one at the normal region and the other at a slightly higher frequency. In these polynuclear alkali metal transition metal-salicylaldehydes, the aldehydic $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and phenolic $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ have been observed not to be in their normal range (Table 1), but invariably higher. This is very suggestive that all these oxygens are bridged ones, bridging the transition metal and, most probably, the alkali metal.

The visible absorption spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ shows typical octahedral absorption bands at 450, 600, and 900 nm. The electronic spectra of alkali metal adducts is different in nature and show one strong band at ~ 600 nm with a shoulder at 550 nm; but the two other peaks of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ are missing. This suggests that the octahedral structure $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ has been converted to tetrahedral structure in its alkali metal adducts. The visible absorption spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$ shows only one band at 550 nm, which is typical of an octahedral cobalt (II) complex. In its alkali metal adducts, this 550 nm band of $\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2$ shift to ~ 650 nm. It is very likely that octahedral $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$ break up into tetrahedral structure in its alkali metal adducts.

The magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of alkali metal adducts reveal a break in polymerised system of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$. Accordingly, the octahedral structure of polymeric nickel-salicylaldehyde and cobalt-salicylaldehyde are converted into a tetrahedral structure of $\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2$ in their alkali metal adducts. The bonding between salicylaldehyde $\text{M}(\text{SalH})_2$ and alkali metal salts, is most likely through the oxygen atoms of aldehydic and phenolic groups, tetrahedrally situated in these cases.

References

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Highly unsaturated ' N_2O_3 ' Ligand System and its Transition Metal Complexes

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THE synthesis of some of the ' N_2O_3 ' type ligands involve the condensation of β -diketones like acetylacetone, substituted acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, dibenzoylmethane, dipivaloylmethane, 3,5-heptanedione *etc.*¹⁻⁴, with aliphatic diamines. However, there are not many reports on the synthesis of the Schiff base ligands with γ -diketones. The conjugated azomethines are considered to be significant because of their relevance to biologically important processes. Rhodopsin, a compound containing conjugated azomethine, is an important intermediate involved in the chemistry of vision⁵. There has been considerable interest in the synthesis and study of quadridentate Schiff base complexes with ' N_2O_3 ' donors^{6,7}. The stereochemistry of the metal complexes of these ligands is found to vary with the length of the methylene chain⁸. The present investigation aims at the synthesis and characterisation of a highly unsaturated ligand derived from benzilmonohydrazone and a γ -diketone, *viz.* acetylacetone and its nickel(II), copper(II) and cobalt(II) complexes.

Experimental

5,8-Dimethyl-1,2,11,12-tetraphenyl-3,4,9,10-tetrazadodeca-2,4,8,10-tetraen-1,12-dione (DTTHD): Benzilmonohydrazone (BMH) (15 g) was dissolved in dry benzene (100 ml) and acetylacetone (8 ml) was added to it and heated under reflux on a water-bath for 12 h. The dark red solution was cooled to 0°. The solid separated was filtered, washed several times with ether, recrystallised from benzene-petrol mixture and finally dried *in vacuo*, m.p. 120° (Found: C, 77.87; H, 6.00; N, 10.24. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$, calcd for: C, 77.56; H, 5.70; N, 10.64%).

General method of preparation of the complexes: To a solution of the ligand DTTHD (0.002 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) metal(II) perchlorate (0.002 mol) was added and the solution was refluxed for 5 h, cooled and filtered. The resulting microcrystalline solid was filtered, washed with water and ether